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An Investigation on the Strategies of Teachers to Manage Undesired Behaviors in the Classroom*

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to define undesirable student behaviors based on the opinions of preschool and classroom teachers and examine teachers' strategies to manage these behaviors. The population of the research consists of classroom teachers and preschool teachers working in Yozgat city center in 2017-2018 academic year. This study is a mixed research in survey model. Qualitative method was conducted via interviews with 11 teachers. Sample of the quantitative method consisted of 227 teachers and data were collected through *inventory of strategies for managing undesired behaviors*. For the analysis of the data content analysis and descriptive analysis were used. As a result of this research, undesirable behaviors were listed under the themes of aggression, non-compliance, interpersonal conflict and irresponsibility. It was observed that students' physical and verbal violence, disturbing each other and damaging the belongings were the most frequent undesirable behaviors in classrooms while the least one was students' irresponsibility for the course such as not doing their homework or not bringing course materials. It was determined that to control the undesired behaviors in classrooms, teachers mostly applied thinking-based strategies, then emotion-based strategies and behavior-based strategies, respectively. Gender was found to be a significant variable in teachers' strategies for managing undesired behavior. In thinking-based strategies, then emotion-based strategies and behavior-based strategies, significant difference was observed in favor of female teachers. However, it was determined that age and years of experience variables did not make a significant difference.

Keywords: Classroom management, undesired behavior, teacher

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Introduction

Education is a wide and long-term process that includes teaching. In this process, in addition to obtaining information in different fields, students acquire life skills such as healthy communication, problem solving, taking rules into account, self-regulation, fulfillment of responsibilities, environmental sensitivity. Classes are the places where students spend most of their time outside their homes. Therefore, the classroom climate and the learning environment are important for achieving the educational objectives. A healthy disciplinary climate is needed to support learning in the classroom, reinforce desired behaviors, minimize undesired behaviors with appropriate strategies and turn them into positive behaviors. Consequently, attention should be paid to undesired student behavior which is one of the factors that can negatively affect the learning process (Yuksel and Ergun, 2005).

Creating desired behaviors and regulating undesirable behaviors of students are important behavioral management issue within the framework of classroom management. First of all, the behaviors of the students in the classroom should be observed carefully and the undesired behaviors should be managed with appropriate strategies. At this point, teachers have a great responsibility because the teacher, beyond being an instructor, is organizer, manager, guide, observer and evaluator (Calik, 2015). Teachers require strategies that can prevent the emergence of undesired student behaviors and can eliminate these behaviors to ensure a disciplined classroom and effective learning environment. Teachers should be able to plan their teaching activities and necessary times carefully, manage unwanted behavior and motivate students (Kucukahmet, 2015; Sarpkaya, 2015). Especially in the first years of education, the determination of undesired behaviors is of great importance in the prevention of negative behaviors that may occur later. Therefore, pre-school and primary school teachers have great responsibility.

Undesired behavior is defined as behaviors that interfere with the teaching process of the teacher, disturb the learning environment directly or indirectly, and create confusion (Burden, 1995). The social environment of a student, the lack of equal learning opportunities, academic failure, unhealthy classroom climate, the social and academic experience of the teacher, and many other factors, which can be classified as in-class and out-of-class factors, can cause undesired behaviors in the classroom (Korkmaz, Korkmaz and Ozkaya, 2009; Yigit, 2004).

Undesired behaviors include all behaviors that lead to a reduction in the effectiveness of learning-teaching activities. Although there are different opinions about what the criteria are in determining these behaviors, there are common points agreed upon. Behaviors that disrupt the course flow, interrupt the activities, prevent the learning of both the student acting the undesired behavior and others, endanger the security and physically harm others are listed as undesirable behaviors encountered in school (Burden, 1995; Korkmaz, 2005; Unal, 2012).

Undesired student behaviors were grouped differently in the literature (Cetin, 2013; Gunduz and Konuk, 2016; Ozturk, 2003; Sadik, 2008). Ozturk (2003) categorizes undesirable behaviors in three categories as academic, social and physical harm. According to Gunduz and Konuk (2016), being disinterested to the lesson, dealing with the distractors in the environment, not doing homework are academically; harming teachers and friends to ensure his/her authority in the classroom, non-compliance with classroom rules are socially; deliberately damaging instructional materials, stealing school materials are physically harmful undesired behaviors. Another classification of undesired student behaviors consists aggressive behaviors that may be verbal and physical, unethical behaviors such as lying, theft, behaviors against authority such as

defiance of authority, interrupting the course with speaking or walking and irresponsible behaviors such as not doing homework (Cetin, 2013; Sadik, 2008).

Undesired behaviors disrupt the learning environment and affect the learning process negatively (Cetin, 2013). The teacher's interest in these behaviors prevents the duration of the lesson to be devoted to learning and causes inefficient use of time (Basar, 2004; Tanhan and Senturk, 2016). Undesired behaviors affect the students' learning process negatively as well as teacher's way of instruction and motivation. It was reported that teachers are more nervous when class discipline cannot be achieved (Basar, 2004; Saritas, 2000). Consequently, these behaviors prevent the creation of a positive class climate. There are different behavior management strategies used by teachers in dealing with undesired behaviors in classroom environment. Some of those are eye contact, warning, showing the right behavior, ignoring, physical intervention, giving responsibility, meeting with school management and family, making changes in the method of teaching, punishing (Korkmaz, 2005; Neyisci-Karakas, 2005). Bentham (2006) explained these strategies by associating them with possible causes. In other words, the possible response to a behavior is given by focusing on the factors that make up it. Based on this assumption, a behavior is shaped according to the results of an individual's past behaviors and emotional and intellectual process. Therefore, strategies that can be used to manage undesired behaviors are explained under three headings; behavior-based, emotion-based, thought-based strategies.

Related studies are considered, there are studies on the undesired student behaviors faced by classroom teachers in primary schools, teachers' methods of coping with these behaviors (Gunduz and Konuk, 2016; Kayıkçı, 2013; Keles, 2010; Keyik, 2014), the effect of the demographic characteristics of students on undesired behaviors (Algozzine, Christian, Marr, McClanahan and White, 2008) and possible solutions (Teyfur, 2015). Gokduman (2007) examined the undesired behaviors of primary school students in public and private primary schools and found that there is no significant difference. Similarly, Armagan, (2010), examined the classroom teachers' ability to cope with undesired behaviors of students in a classroom in a private elementary school. Studies on undesired behaviors have been addressed at the level of students in pre-primary schools (Cosan, 2017) and at secondary level (Bayar and Kerns, 2015). Cothran, Pamela, Kulinna and Garrahy (2009) evaluated the causes and consequences of undesired student behaviors from the perspective of students and teachers. The existence of studies related to undesired behaviors in the literature increases in parallel with the importance attributed to class undesired behaviors.

Nowadays, it is observed that the undesired student behaviors faced by the teachers in the classroom has also diversified in the context of changing circumstances. Especially, in the period of preschool and primary school which are the beginning years of the education, undesired behaviors of children should be defined. There would be better solutions if the problems are defined clearly. Therefore, defining what are the undesired behaviors encountered in classrooms according to teachers' opinions and determining what strategies are used to regulate these behaviors are thought to be necessary and essential for the literature. Therefore, in this study, it is aimed to determine the opinions of classroom teachers and preschool teachers working in Yozgat city center on undesirable student behavior and their strategies to manage these behaviors. In this context, answers to the following questions are sought;

1. What are the undesired behaviors in the classroom according to teachers' opinions?
2. What are teachers' strategies to manage undesired behaviors?

Method

In this part, research design of the study was explained. The population and sample of the quantitative method and study group of the qualitative method were presented. Details of data collection tools and analysis were also presented.

Research Design

The study is a mixed research in the survey model. Survey research aims to describe the characteristics of individuals, groups or organizations of interest in their current situation (Berends, 2006; Karasar, 2005). Mixed research is a research approach asserting that qualitative and quantitative methods or paradigms can be used together in a single study (Balci, 2017). In the study, "convergent parallel design" was used in mixed method research. Data are collected simultaneously in the convergent parallel design. During the analysis phase of this pattern, the qualitative and quantitative data of the research are analyzed separately and the results are interpreted by combining the results (Creswell and PlanoClark, 2014). In the study the explanation of undesired behaviors were collected and analyzed with qualitative method while teachers' strategies for managing undesired behaviors were analyzed through quantitative method.

Study Group, Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of 341 preschool and classroom teachers working in Yozgat city center in 2017-2018. Before data collection, legal permission of Yozgat Provincial Directorate of National Education and ethical approval of Yozgat Bozok University were obtained. In the qualitative part of the study, criterion sampling was used and data were collected from a study group consisting of 11 class and preschool teachers. The study group constituted teachers having at least five years of experience and who had been working in the same school for at least three years. For quantitative analysis, the theoretical sample size chart was used to determine the sample size (Balci, 2017). Considering the size of the population consisting of 341 teachers, sample size representing the population at a confidence level of 95% was found as 172 teachers. In this study, the sample selection from the population was made according to the random sampling method. Demographic data of the participants are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Data of the participants

Variables		N	%
Gender	Female	121	53.30
	Male	106	46.70
Age	20-30	21	9.25
	31-40	107	47.14
	41-50	56	24.67
	51-60	26	11.45
	Over 61	17	7.49
Seniority	1-5	17	7.49
	6-10	61	26.87
	11-15	46	20.26
	16-20	39	17.18
	21+	64	28.19
Classroom level	Preschool	57	25.11
	1 st Class	40	17.62
	2 nd Class	47	20.70
	3 rd Class	40	17.62
	4 th Class	43	18.94
Branch	Classroom teacher	169	74.45
	Preschool teacher	57	25.55
Total		227	100

As can be seen in Table 1, 53.30% of the participants were women and 46.70% were men. 169 of them were classroom teachers while 57 of them were preschool teachers. According to their age, 9.25% of the participants were between the ages of 20-30, 47.14% of them were between 31-40; 24.67% of them were between 41-50; 11.45% of them were between 51-60, and 7.49% of them were 61 and older. It was seen that 57 of the participant teachers work in preschools, while 40 of them were in the first class, 47 of them were in the second class, 40 of them were in the third year and 43 of them were in the fourth class.

Data Collection Tools

Teacher Interview Form for Determining Undesired Behavior in the Classroom: The form developed by the researcher aims to determine teachers' opinions on what undesired behaviors in the classroom are, which is the primary purpose of the research. The teacher interview form for determining undesired behaviors in the classroom was formed with a semi-structured interview approach. During the interview's teachers were asked to define the undesired behaviors they meet in their classes. It included the questions "what are the behaviors that you define as undesired?", "what are the most undesired behaviors that you meet in your classes?" and "what are your evaluation towards undesired behaviors?". For the demographic data, teachers' gender, age, level of education and their years of experience were asked.

Inventory of Strategies for Managing Undesired Behaviors (ISMUB): The inventory developed by the researcher to determine teachers' strategies for managing undesired behaviors consists of three sub-scales: *behavior-based strategies scale*, *emotion-based strategies scale* and *thinking-based strategies scale*. In the development of the scales, KMO and Barlett values were checked and found appropriate for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The results of EFA revealed single factor structure for each scale. The scales are the 5-point Likert in which each item is scored

from “always (5)” to “never (1)”. The *behavior-based strategies scale* consists of 19 items, *emotion-based strategies scale* consists of 15 items and *thinking-based strategies scale* consists of 9 items. Within the scope of the study, structural validity and reliability analyses of the scales were carried out and Cronbach alpha coefficients of scales were determined as .81; .85 and .83, respectively.

Data Analysis

In this study, 11 teachers (3 preschool teacher and 8 classroom teacher) were interviewed to determine what the undesired student behaviors they experienced in their courses. The data were analyzed by content analysis. The main purpose of content analysis is to reach concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data (Yildirim and Simsek, 2013). For the quantitative part of the study, data collection tool was distributed to 250 teachers. 23 of the inventories were excluded as they had missing data and 227 of the responses were found to be suitable for analysis. Before the analysis, normality of the data was checked. The skewness coefficients of the *behavior-based strategies scale*, *emotion-based strategies scale* and *thinking-based strategies scale* was between -.407 - -.930; -.747 - -1.133; -1.124 - -1.456, respectively. Kurtosis coefficients of the scales were .318 – 1.48; .111 - .494; .416 – 1.543, respectively. The coefficients were within the acceptance range for normality (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). Based on the results, parametric analysis was conducted. For the analysis of the data SPSS was used. Arithmetic mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (Sd) values were found in order to determine teachers' views on behavior-based strategies, emotion-based strategies and thinking-based strategies in order to determine strategies for managing undesired behaviors.

Findings

In this section, according to teacher opinions, undesirable behaviors in the classroom and the strategies of managing the undesired behavior used by teachers in the classroom are presented.

Regarding the Critical Thinking Tendency

Identification of undesired behaviors in classroom

In the qualitative part of the research, the data obtained at the end of the semi-structured interview were examined by content analysis. As a result of the analysis, undesirable behaviors were collected under four themes called aggression, incompatibility with rules, interpersonal conflict and irresponsibility. Teachers' views and themes for defining undesirable behavior are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Themes of undesirable behaviors in classroom

Themes	Codes	f
Aggression	Physical and verbal violence	8
	Harassing friends (Bad words, disrespect, etc.)	7
	Damaging other's property	4
	Total	19
Non-Compliance Rules	with Non-compliance with class rules	7
	Moving without permission (walking in class, etc.)	3
	Total	10
Interpersonal Conflict	Complaining about friends	3
	Feelings such as jealousy, non-sharing	2
	Disturbing behavior during class	2
	Total	7
Irresponsibility	Unprepared for class	1
	Lack of material	1
	Total	2
Total		38

As can be seen in Table 2, according to the teachers' opinions, undesirable behaviors in the classroom were grouped under the themes of aggression (f = 19), non-compliance with rules (f = 10), interpersonal conflict (f = 7) and irresponsibility (f = 2). The most frequently expressed undesired behaviors of students are under the theme of aggression. Irresponsibility was determined as the lowest frequency theme.

When Table 2 is examined, within the scope of aggression theme, 8 of the teacher's opinions on undesired behavior in the classroom were collected under the code of "physical and verbal violence". 7 of the teacher's opinions were coded for "harassing friends" and 4 were codes "damaging other's property". Accordingly, behaviors resulting from aggression are the most frequent undesired behaviors of students in the classroom. The participants stated their views as:

"Physical violence is the most important undesired behavior to me. As teachers, we can control students in class, but it is more difficult to control them from harming each other during breaks. I can say that we hear complaints like "he hit me, pushed me, dropped me" nearly at the beginning of every lesson".

“One of the common problems we encounter among students in younger age groups is that they physically hurt each other. They could push or kick each other for very simple reasons, like he/she sat on my desk, he/she did not give me a place to walk”.

Students can disturb each other not only physically but also verbally in the classroom. In this regard, the participants stated the following:

“Students’ pushing each other and saying bad words are the most common undesirable behaviors in the classes. Sometimes they call each other with negative nicknames and make fun of each other. This situation is really annoying for the student who is being mocked, and it discourages him/her”.

“In this period, children perceive slang as a nice quality. They can say the words they learned from the street to their friends. They can also disturb each other by talking negatively about of his friend”.

Undesired behavior in the classroom both disrupts the lesson and negatively affects the classroom climate. As stated by the teachers above, students' physical harm to each other and using negative slang words are among the factors that disrupt the classroom climate.

With globalization, the world is getting smaller and with the spread of communication tools, different cultures are getting closer to each other more than ever before. One of the values that students should gain in such a period is to respect differences and to have good communication skills. Students who can express themselves well and listen patiently can solve their problems without physical or verbal violence. Therefore, it is very important to prevent physical and verbal violence in the classroom and school, and to provide students having good communication skills.

Also, when this situation cannot be controlled, it can lead bullying that can have many negative consequences. Another teacher stated this as:

“Students, starting from preschool education, should learn not to harm their environment, especially state property. However, we see that students are careless about the use of desks and the use of toilets. I even saw a student trying to scratch off the paint on the wall”.

“In fact, when a negative behavior is displayed, its consequences are generally negative. For example, when one takes his friend's belongings without permission and harms them, the child gets angry and tries to hit him/her or damage his /her properties”.

Education is the process of creating a desired behavior change. This ‘desired’ change involves sense of responsibility towards the society. For this reason, students should learn to protect their belongings and not to harm their environment even if they do not belong to them. This sensitivity should be gained primarily in the family and then in the first period of education. However, if this sensitivity is not gained sufficiently, students may harm their environment.

Secondly undesired behaviors that are most frequently experienced by teachers are grouped under the theme of Non-Compliance with rules. These undesired behaviors are "non-compliance with class rules" (f=7) and " moving without permission "(f=3). Participants stated that followings for this theme

“As you know every teacher has his/her own rules in a class. I always want students to ask my permission. However, sometimes some students can stroll around the classroom. For example, they go to the toilet without permission. Of course they will go when they need, but I prefer them to ask my permission first. Otherwise it an undesired behavior for me”.

“We set the rules at the beginning of the semester in order to keep the course in order. These are basic arrangements, such as asking permission to speak, being ready and sitting

on their desk after the ring for the lesson. However, sometimes there may be problems in implementing. When I enter the classroom, some students are still running around and this delays me starting the class”

“I want the student to have full attention for a proper and effective lesson. To achieve this, we create a certain order in the classroom. The game must be played during the game time, the activity must be held during the activity time. When the students do not obey these rules, there occurs confusion and the activity does not achieve its purpose. Therefore, it bothers me when the students do not obey the classroom rules”.

The aim of the teaching is to gain students the targeted behaviors and to realize their learning at the highest level. This is only possible in a disciplined learning environment. For this reason, all teachers expect students to follow the lesson in a regular manner. When students act without permission and do not obey the determined class rules, it negatively affects the effectiveness of the learning environment. Also, it sets a negative example for other students.

Under the theme of interpersonal conflict, codes such as "complaining about friends", "feelings such as jealousy, not sharing" and "disturbing behavior during class" were included. The explanation of the participants for the complaining code as follows:

“One of undesired behaviors is students’ complaining about each other. Of course, important situations need to be told the teacher. However, they tell me all issues as complaints which they normally need to deal with among themselves like "teacher he/she does not get up from my desk, does not give me room to sharpen my pencil, scribbles on the blackboard, touches my hair”.

“Sometimes a student really complains a situation that really bothers him/her, but mostly it is about things that are not serious and they can handle among themselves. They constantly observe each other's negative behavior and complain in the slightest situation”.

One of the most important features that education systems aim to gain students within the 21st century is problem solving. It is aimed to raise individuals who can adapt to constantly changing conditions, take responsibility for their own learning, solve the problems they encounter and produce different solutions. In this case, it is expected that students will be able to establish a healthy communication and solve problems not by complaining but by seeking different solutions from the very beginning periods of their education.

Another code of this theme was feelings such as jealousy, non-sharing. Participants stated the followings for these codes as follows:

“Students can get jealous of each other. They may even be jealous of your interest, as teachers, in other students . Actually, we pay attention to this issue, but still, students perceive the events differently”.

Another undesired behavior observed among students is interpersonal conflict. Students disturbing each other during the lesson distract them from learning. This also prevents the course from being progressed effectively. Moreover, not sharing can turn into conflict among the students, which may cause them to complain to each other constantly. These are classified among undesired behavior by teachers. Two of the teachers explained it as follows:

“Students can disturb each other during the lesson. In the break times, problems such as toy fights or not sharing materials are common”.

“Sometimes students continue to communicate with each other during the lesson. I mean by communication, they draw pictures or try to send notes to each other. In this case, she/he focuses entirely on that note and her/his friend. This means that the course cannot be learned for both students. It is difficult when the students are not mentally ready even though they are physically in the class”.

The least mentioned theme is irresponsibility which comprises the codes “unprepared for class” and “lack of material”. Two teachers explained it as:

“Forgetting the course materials and coming to class without doing homework negatively affect the course flow”

“Especially in this age group, the lesson should be concretized. For example, we use number beads, abacus at the beginning of math class. I want every student to bring these to class. When the student does not bring it that day, it becomes difficult for him to understand the lesson and it also negatively affects his desk mate as he/she uses his/her desk mate’s material. It is same when a student does not bring his book on a story reading day”.

For the effectiveness of the lesson, it is very important that the students are prepared and ready for the class. This preparation includes both the mental readiness and the preliminary preparations, such as doing the homework related to the lesson and bringing the necessary materials. When students do not make the preparations, their level of preparedness is low. In this case, some course time need to be devoted to the preparation phase. The time allocated for actual teaching becomes limited. Irresponsibility of students is an important obstacle in a learning environment where the time is limited. In this direction, it is of great importance that students gain a sense of responsibility. In today’s education system, where learning to learn is the motto, students are expected not only to learn their current lessons but also to be ready for new learning situations they will encounter, and to be aware of their learning skills and responsibilities at this point.

Teachers' strategies to manage undesired behaviors

Table 3 represents the strategies of teachers to manage undesired behaviors in the classroom.

Table 3. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of teachers’ strategies for managing undesired behaviors

Scales	\bar{X}	Sd.
Behavior-Based Strategies	3.47	6.71
Emotion-Based Strategies	4.67	4.58
Thinking-Based Strategies	4.71	2.65

As seen from Table 3, it is observed that teachers mostly apply thinking-based strategies ($\bar{X} = 4.71$). The next preferences of the teachers were emotion-based strategies ($\bar{X}= 4.67$) and the least adopted strategies were behavior-based strategies ($\bar{X}= 3.47$). Table 4 presents the difference test for teachers’ management of undesired behaviors according to gender variable.

Table 4. Results of t-test for comparison of teachers' management of undesired behaviors by gender

Scales	Gender	\bar{X}	Sd	df	t	p
Behavior-Based Strategies	Female	67.16	6.34	208	2.517	0.013*
	Male	64.86	6.91			
Emotion-Based Strategies	Female	70.75	4.32	199.25	3.917	0.000*
	Male	68.16	5.46			
Thinking-Based Strategies	Female	33.25	2.35	201.952	2.675	0.007*
	Male	32.30	2.90			

*p<.05

As seen in Table 4, the mean scores of female teachers' strategies for managing in-class misbehavior in "Behavior-Based Strategies", "Emotion-Based Strategies" and "Thinking-Based Strategies" are higher than the mean scores of male teachers. There are significant differences between the averages by gender [t (208)= 2.517, p< .05; t (195.25)= 3.917; p< .05; t (201.952)= 2.675, p< .05]. Table 5 presents the difference test for teachers' management of undesired behaviors according to age variable.

Table 5. Results of ANOVA for comparison of teachers' management of undesired behaviors by age

Scales	Age	N	\bar{X}	Sd	F	p
Behavior-Based Strategies	20-30	20	67.45	4.75	0.998	0.410
	31-40	104	66.51	6.70		
	41-50	47	65.36	7.43		
	51-60	24	64.08	7.38		
	61 +	15	66.53	5.20		
Emotion-Based Strategies	20-30	21	70.71	4.08	0.462	0.764
	31-40	108	69.38	4.72		
	41-50	54	69.44	5.59		
	51-60	26	68.96	5.75		
	61 +	17	70.17	5.41		
Thinking-Based Strategies	20-30	21	32.71	2.66	0.624	0.646
	31-40	107	32.84	2.63		
	41-50	56	32.57	2.88		
	51-60	26	32.65	2.75		
	61 +	17	33.70	1.79		

*p<.05

As seen in Table 5, age variable is not a significant variable for teachers' strategies for managing undesired behaviors in Behavior-Based Strategies, Emotion-Based Strategies, Thinking-Based Strategies [(F=0.998; p>.05; F= 0.462, p> .05; F= 0.624, p> .05), respectively]. Table 6 presents the difference test for teachers' management of undesired behaviors according to years of experience variable.

Table 6. Results of ANOVA for comparison of teachers' management of undesired behaviors by years of experience

Scales	Years of experience	N	\bar{X}	Sd	F	p
Behavior-Based Strategies	1-5	16	65.06	6.24	1.000	0,409
	6-10	57	67.29	5.99		
	11-15	46	66.08	7.27		
	16-20	32	66.40	6.12		
	21+	59	64.94	7.28		
Emotion-Based Strategies	1-5	17	70.23	4.33	0.466	0.761
	6-10	60	70.06	4.52		
	11-15	48	68.87	5.16		
	16-20	37	69.48	5.48		
	21+	64	69.37	5.40		
Thinking-Based Strategies	1-5	17	33.00	2.59	0,647	0,958
	6-10	61	32.47	3.12		
	11-15	46	33.28	1.91		
	16-20	39	32.33	3.27		
	21+	64	33.01	2.18		

*p<.05

As seen in Table 6, years of experience is not a significant variable for teachers' strategies for managing undesired behaviors in Behavior-Based Strategies, Emotion-Based Strategies, Thinking-Based Strategies [(F= 1.000, p> .05; F= 0.466, p> .05; F= 0.647, p> .05), respectively]. Interpretation of all results were given in the discussion and conclusion part of the study.

Discussion and Conclusion

This research aims to identify the undesired behaviors in the classroom according to the teachers' opinions and to describe which strategy teachers prefer in the face of undesired behaviors. In the qualitative part of the study, undesirable behaviors were grouped under four themes called aggression, non-compliance with rules, interpersonal conflict and irresponsibility. The most frequently encountered undesired behavior of the teachers in the classroom was found to be behaviors in the theme of aggression. Physical and verbal violence of students towards each other is the most common behavior that teachers encounter in classrooms. This finding is consistent with Dada and Okunade (2014), who stated that bullying, noise, abuse of words, fighting and violent actions were the most common undesired behaviors in the classroom. Similarly, Sakallioğlu (2014) reported aggressive attitude towards school and teachers and physical harm to friends among the most common undesired behaviors. The students' non-compliance with the classroom rules and their unauthorized behaviors were noted under the theme of non-compliance with the rules. When studies conducted in the literature are reviewed, these results show parallelism. Dal (2016) found that the most undesirable behaviors stated by teachers as not obeying the classroom rules and complaining about their friends. Similarly, Danaoğlu (2009) stated that students' talking with each other in the lesson without taking right to speak, and their intentional disruption of the course flow were among the most undesired behaviors that classroom teachers encounter most. Each of the preschool and primary school students comes from different families and different socio-cultural contexts. It can be stated that the education process that started primarily in families is carried out in schools in a planned and desired manner. Social rules and class norms are not fully adopted by students at the beginning of the education process. Therefore, the physical and verbal violence

practices of the students within the study and their behaviors of not recognizing the rules can be explained in this context.

In this study, the theme of interpersonal conflict took place in the third rank of undesirable behaviors defined by teachers. This finding is consistent with the studies suggesting that disagreements between students and complaining about each other are common behaviors in preschool (Cengin-Unuvar, 2014; Neyisci-Karakas, 2005; Ozer, Bozkurt and Tuncay, 2014). The last theme, irresponsibility included the least expressed undesired behaviors such as coming to the lesson unprepared, not bringing the material, and not doing homework. In this study, the low frequency of irresponsibility contact may be because of the problems related to classroom order in the first period of education. In the initial phase of the education process, teachers primarily focus on unwanted physical behaviors to create a suitable learning environment. Teachers can primarily aim to create a regular learning environment in the classroom and to establish healthy relationships among students. Therefore, expected behaviors of students regarding school and academic learning may fall behind. This situation may explain that the last stated undesired behavior was the irresponsible behaviors of the students regarding the lesson. However, this result contradicts with the findings of Danaoglu (2009). Danaoglu (2009) reported not doing homework, not performing the tasks given as the most undesirable behavior of classroom teachers.

The second study question examined what strategies teachers use to manage undesired behavior. As a result of the research, it was determined that teachers applied the most thinking-based strategies, then emotion-based strategies and Behavior-Based Strategies, respectively. When the items included in the scales were examined, it was found out that the items "I talk to the student about his behavior", "I ask the student why s/he misbehaves", "I remind the rules of our class" and "I talk to the student after class" had higher scores, while items "I threaten the student", "I send the student out of the class", "I send the student to the principal" and "I physically interfere with the student" had the lowest average score.

The results of the study show that teachers primarily try to raise awareness about what is undesired behavior in students and start a process for correcting those behaviors. Teachers emphasize on making students feel worthy and motivating them to act positively. Teachers' last preferred strategy is punishing the student for undesired behavior. These findings are in line with Neyisci-Karakas's (2005) research. Similarly, Sakallioğlu (2014) stated that teachers' most common strategies against undesired behaviors were providing a clear understanding of the rules that define what is expected, establishing a warm and respectful relationship between the student and the teacher, and using positive reinforcement to maintain good behavior and turn bad behavior into positive. He stated that the least resorted strategy for teachers was rebuke. Today, within the framework of the constructivist approach, students are required to take part in the teaching processes and to be in the process from determining the rules to the evaluation. In this direction, it is understandable that teachers took part in the study preferred thinking-based strategies and encouraged students to think about the undesirable behaviors they exhibit.

This study aims to identify undesired behaviors in the classroom and to determine undesired behavior management strategies relying on the opinions of preschool and elementary school teachers. The most frequently observed undesirable behavior by teachers in their classrooms was the physical and verbal violence of the students, students' disturbing each other and damaging the belongings. The least undesired behavior was students' not taking responsibility for the course, such as not doing their homework or bringing course materials. As a result of the research, it was determined that the teachers mostly applied thinking-based strategies, followed by emotion-based strategies and behavior-based strategies, respectively.

Based on the findings of this research, it was found that the undesirable behaviors encountered in the classroom were mostly related to the order of the class. According to this result, it can be said that teachers spend more time to ensure the order in the classroom. To reach the desired level, the time allocated to instruction should be increased both quantitatively and qualitatively. It is important to minimize undesired behaviors in the classroom with appropriate strategies. In this context, it would be useful for prospective teachers to take applied class management courses more effectively during their training programs. Professional development activities related to undesirable behavior management would be helpful both for novice and veteran teachers. School principals are recommended to organize activities collaborating with parents and sportive and social activities which help students spend their energy and increase their loyalty to the school. These activities can minimize undesirable behaviors of students. This study is limited to preschool and primary school teachers working in Yozgat center. Repeating the research in different regions and at different levels may provide a broader information on undesirable behaviors.

Students' undesired behaviors and teachers' management strategies for these behaviors can be in relation with various variables such as school principal, school environment and students. Researchers are advised to examine all these relationships. Teachers' strategies of managing undesired behaviors could affect students' school engagement, motivation, attitudes and behaviors. Students' demographic variables such as their socio-cultural and socio-economic background may affect the way students behave in classes. So future studies on these variables would be beneficial. Undesirable behavior can have a mediating effect on these variables. Therefore, the mediating role of undesired behaviors on school attitudes can be examined. Principals are primarily responsible for school administration. Their leadership styles influence a school's climate, culture, academic vision, teachers' organizational behaviors. Therefore, researchers can be advised to examine the relationships between teachers' strategies and variables related to principals and school. It is essential to remember that the goal of education is to prevent undesired behaviors before they occur. Therefore, it would be useful to conduct qualitative studies with students for a detail examination of the reasons of their undesirable behaviors. Furthermore, conducting qualitative studies on teachers' coping strategies for misbehavior will be useful to find out which strategy they use for various situations and to determine successful strategies.

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